

Analysis and Prediction of Soybean Plant Disease

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CSV, LibSVM, and c\$.5's format.

Abstract-Disease detection of the plant is one of the absorbing research areas in the farming field. This field needs a dependable prediction methodology to understand elements influencing disease. Plant diseases become major threats for us because it harms our body by reducing our immune system and also degrade the quality of crops. As the production of soybean is decreased due to natural hazard, overuse of pesticides, soil problem, and lack of agricultural knowledge and mainly due to diseases.

Analyzing data from different aspects and summarizing it into valuable information is the operation done in machine learning. It permits users to analyses data from different dimensions, categorize and the relationships are identified. WEKA is a data analysis tool for machine learning classification. Machine learning classification is a vital technique with more applications in various fields. It is used to classify each item in a set of data into one predefined set of classes. This paper presents the analysis of soybean plant diseases based on the dataset of plant growth, seed germination, damaged area, external decay, leafspot size, seed discolor, etc. The proposed work focuses on machine learning techniques and using the WEKA tool.

I. INTRODUCTION

WEKA was developed by Waikato University, New Zealand. WEKA - Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis. It provides different pre-processing, machine learning algorithms, data mining tools. It includes an algorithm for: classification, clustering, regression, association rule mining, attribute selection. It also has data visualization facilities. WEKA is open-source software. It provides tools for data pre-processing, implementation of several Machine Learning algorithms, and visualization tools so that you can develop machine learning techniques and apply them to real-world data mining problems. WEKA stores data in ARFF file format. It is easy to transform the EXCEL file to the ARFF format. An ARFF file consists of a list of instances. We can create an ARFF file by using Notepad or word. The name of the dataset is with @relation. Attribute information is with @attribute. The data is with @data. Besides the ARFF format, WEKA allows

Fusarium root rot, pythium disease, soybean cyst nematode, Rhizoctonia root rot are the root diseases seen in the soybean plant. Stem and wilt diseases are bacterial wilt, fusarium yellows, stem rot, and white mold. Anthracnose, bacterial brown spot, bean common mosaic, common bean root dust are the foliar diseases. The above diseases are the important types of soybean diseases. Identification and prediction of soybean plant disease at the beginning of the disease is a better method to prevent the disease from spreading. The ARFF file used in WEKA for disease prediction of soybean plants contains the details of many soybean plants and their symptoms. Machine learning algorithms and data mining techniques are widely used for prediction and classification. The J48 and Naive Bayesian algorithm is used for classification. These are the best machine learning algorithms.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Dr. J. Annrose, Dr. N. Herald Anantha Rufus, Dr. C. R. Edwin Selva Rex, Dr. D. Godwin Immanuel [1], "Soybean Plant Disease Classification using Archimedes Optimization Algorithm based Hybrid Deep Learning Model". A large data set containing healthy image classes and four unhealthy image classes like Bean halo blight, Rhizoctonia root rot, Pythium diseases, Anthracnose are used. MATLAB software is used for implementing the HDL-AOA model for bean disease classification. The steps involved in the HDL-AOA model for bean classification are wavelet packet decomposition, long short-term memory networks, Archimedes optimization algorithm (AOA) for multiple single LSTM networks, Hybrid deep learning model for the classification model. The HDL-AOA produces the result in percentage. And it also demonstrates the accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, precision, recall, and F-score values.

Predrag Randelvoic, Vuk Dordevic, Stanko Milic, Svetlana Balesevic-Tubic, Kristina Petrovic, Jegor Miladinovic, and Vojin Dukic [2], "Prediction of Soybean Plant Density using a Machine Learning Model and Vegetation Indices Extracted from RGB Images Taken with a UAV". Agricultural production is mainly depending on plant density. The soybean plant density is analyzed using RGB images taken with UAV. RRD, BLUE, GREEN are

the channels in RGB. For each plot the mean values of R, G, B were extracted, then vegetative indices were derived and it is used for predictions in Machine Learning Model (MML). Random Forest (RF) is used for calculation and classification. The large set of data is classified using many trees that are used by RF. The predictions are done based on the data get from the tree.

Tamara Saad Mohamed [3], “Heart Disease Prediction Using WEKA”. Based on the lifestyle of people the day-by-day heart disease is increasing and create risk in people’s life. The decision tree J-48 and Naive Bayesian algorithm are used to predict heart diseases by using medical data containing details of patients with cholesterol, blood pressure, chest pain, blood sugar, etc. By comparing the output of both J-48 and Naive Bayesian algorithms the final output is predicted.

Henrique Pozebon, Alberto Cargnelutti Filho, Jerson V. Guedes, Dener R. Ferreria, Rafael P. Marques, Julia G. Bevilaqua, Leonardo S. Patias, Tiago L. Colpo & Jonas A. Amemann [4], “Distribution of Bemisia tabaci within soybean plants and on individual leaflets: Whitefly distribution on soybean plants”. It is important to control the whiteflies on the soybean plant. Whiteflies on soybean plants in the greenhouse and other field conditions can be controlled by distributing the Bemisia tabaci on soybean plants and leaflets. To calculate the whitefly nymphs, collected leaflets are arranged in 32 sections with eight rows and four columns. Following different calculations like the Morisita index, dispersion index the leaf type with the highest whitefly were identified.

Chandradeep Bhatt, Anubhooti Papola [5], “Analysis and Prediction of Landslides in Uttarakhand Using Weka Tool”. Analysis and prediction of landslides susceptible and non-susceptible areas are done using the WEKA tool. The techniques used for analyzing landslides are J48 and LMT. And predicting landslides using MATLAB. Data with ARFF extension is used for predicting and analyzing landslides. After classifying the data, the landslide prediction model obtained from the WEKA is implemented in MATLAB. Then, inputting some land details in MATLAB we have an idea that the area is susceptible or non-susceptible.

III.METHODOLOGY

After opening the WEKA. The WEKA GUI Chooser application will start and you would see the following screen. As shown in “Fig. 1”.

Fig.1. Screen appears after open WEKA

The GUI Chooser application allows you to run five different types of applications as listed here –

- Explorer
- Experimenter
- Knowledge Flow
- Workbench
- Simple CLI

We need to click on the workbench. Then a window is open as shown in “Fig. 2”.

Fig.2. WEKA workbench

Then we open the dataset. The dataset that is used for the analysis and prediction of soybean plant disease is an ARFF extension file as shown in “Fig.3”.

	date	plant-stand	precip	temp	crop-hist	area-damaged	severity	seed-tmt	germination	plant-growth	leaves	leafspots-halo	leafspots-marg	leafspots-size	leaf-shred	leaf-mild	leaf-severe
73	august	normal	lt-norm	gt-norm	yes	same-field	whole-field	pot-severe	Fungicide	lt-80	norm	abnorm	absent	dna	dna	absent	absent
137	may	lt-normal	gt-norm	norm	yes	same-field	whole-field	pot-severe	none	lt-80	norm	abnorm	no-yellow-halos	w-s-marg	gt-1/8	present	absent
220	october	normal	gt-norm	gt-norm	yes	same-field	whole-field	minor	Fungicide	80-89	norm	abnorm	no-yellow-halos	w-s-marg	gt-1/8	absent	absent
302	July				same-field	low-areas					abnorm	abnorm					
344	July	lt-normal	norm	norm	same-field	low-areas					abnorm	abnorm	absent	dna	dna	absent	absent
351	July	lt-normal	gt-norm	gt-norm	same-field	low-areas					abnorm	abnorm					

Fig.3. Dataset of soybean

There are 36 attributes in the dataset. Some of them are:

- Date
- Plant stand
- Crop hist
- Area damaged
- Fruit-spots
- Fruit-pods
- Germination
- Stem
- Hail

Data preprocessing is the next level is to do. Data preprocessing transforms the data into a new form that is suitable to perform mining algorithms. 36 attributes are selected to preprocessing data with 683 instances and 0% missing values in our data. Data preprocessing of soybean data is shown in “Fig.4”.

Fig.4. Soybean dataset preprocessing

The visualization of all attributes is shown “Fig.4.1”.

Fig.4.1. Visualization of all attributes

Then classify the data using the J48 algorithm. J48 is a decision-tree-based algorithm. It is an algorithm in machine learning for classifying data categorically and continuously. It measures improved performance and produces a higher rate of accuracy [3].

A. Algorithm J48:

Input I // Training data

Output O // Decision tree

DTBUILD (*I) (O-Null):

I = Generate root node and label with splitting attribute;

I = Attach arc to root node for each split predict and label;

For each arc do

I = Database created by applying to splitting predict to I;

If the termination point reached for this path, then

O' = Create leaf node and label with appropriate class;

Else O' = DTBUILD(I);

O = Add O' to arc;

J48 ignores the missing value during the time of building the tree. The J48 algorithm produces the following output shown in “Fig.5”.

Fig.5. Output of the J48 algorithm

The tree formed using the J48 algorithm is shown in “Fig.5.1”. The mold growth is the root node. If mold growth is present, then further analyze the precip. If the precip is normal, then analyzing the plant-stand then it is normal. If the mold growth is absent, then it analyzing the seed discolor. If the seed discolors are present, then the plant is abnormal. Otherwise, it checks the seed size. If the seed size is not normal, then it checks the plant growth and finally predicts the plant is normal or abnormal.

Fig.5.1. Tree of J48 algorithm

B. Naive Bayesian Classifier

The result of Naive Bayes Classifier is shown in “Fig.6”. Naive Bayes classifier is a classification algorithm based on Bayes Theorem. It is especially fit when the dimensionality of input is high. It is work based on the following Bayesian equation:

$$P(T/S) = [P(S/T) * P(T)] / P(S)$$

Fig.6 Result of Naive Bayes classifier

IV.RESULT

The cost analysis of a diaporthe-stem-canker class of the J48 algorithm is shown in “Fig.7”. The threshold curve and cost/benefit curve and produced in cost analysis.

Fig.7. Result of Cost analysis of a diaporthe-stem-canker class of the J48 algorithm.

The cost analysis of a diaporthe-stem-canker class of the Naive Bayes classifier is shown in “Fig.8”.

Fig.8. Result of cost analysis of a diaporthe-stem-canker class of the Naive Bayes classifier

V.CONCLUSION

After applying both J48 and Naive Bayesian algorithm on the soybean dataset the results are given in “Fig.9”.

Evaluation Criteria	Naive Bayes	J48
Time is taken to build the model	0.02 seconds	0 seconds
Incorrectly classified instances	635	625
Correctly classified instances	48	58
Prediction accuracy	92.9722%	91.5081%

Fig.9. Result comparison of Naïve Bayes Classifier and J48 algorithm

Comparing the accuracy rate, we can conclude that the Naive Bayes algorithm is more efficient than the J48 algorithm. This paper results to predict the disease of a soybean plant by analyzing different factors such as seed-discolor, precip, seed size, etc. The diseases like Rhizoctonia root rot, Pythium diseases, Anthracnose, etc.

VI.FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we analyze and predict the soybean plant disease. But here we didn’t find the organic or chemical medicines to prevent or remove the diseases. So, the future work we can do is can suggest the proper medicine for each disease that is predicted by the J48 and Naive Bayesian algorithm. For this medicine suggestion, we will use another dataset containing attributes like name of the disease, name of medicine

VII.REFERENCES

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